

EVOLVING LIBRARY AS A LEARNING RESOURCE CENTRE BY ADOPTING BEST PRACTICES

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Abstract

Technology has power to change services offer by library in current scenario and it has positive impact on users too. The earlier source of storage of knowledge was human mind which has been transfer to manuscripts, print and non-print materials and now a days it's in the air/virtual or cloud based. To attract users towards learning resources available at library, existing services has to be changed according to changing demands from its users and therefore, technology has playing vital role in this regards. With help of the state of the art technology library can offer its users need based services the same has been discussed in this article.

Keywords : Information Technology, Learning Resource Centre, QR Code, Best Practices

In the Higher Education Institutions, library has playing very important role to inculcate reading habit amongst the learners and create research environment at college level. A study says, stake holders of HEI spending their valuable time at library to complete their assigned work to be fulfilled to get degree certificate from University. The score achieved in final examination has its own importance for their carrier but time spends for research study at the library will give them some extra insights to be served to our society.

Library can channelize such research activities through their services, therefore it is important to accomplish requisite of learners. Fulfilment of learners can be achieved by promoting library services and creating interactive environment at reading places. By adopting of suitable best practices for optimum utilization of existing learning resources, learners' performance will have positive impact on their own carrier.

Evolving library as a learning resource centre can be done by adopting following best practices at our library;

1. Title of the practice – QR Code enabled access to Journals and Magazines

Goals –

- To inculcate reading habit amongst the learners
- To create awareness of available learning resource at library

The Context –

QR code (abbreviated from Quick Response Code) is the trademark for a type of matrix barcode (or two-dimensional barcode) first designed of the automotive industry in Japan. A barcode is a machine-readable optical label that contains information about the item to which it is attached. A QR code uses four standardized encoding modes (numeric, alphanumeric, byte/binary, and kanji) to efficiently store data; extensions may also be used. (Source - https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/QR_code)

QR code can be generated online, and same has to paste on Journals and Magazines. Users need to be installed the QR code scanner to read the barcode which has been link with Journals and Magazines full text current issue.

Image of QR Code

Evidence of Success –

Users are quite excited with this service provided by central library; it has positive impact on their learning skills. Visits of digital library surprisingly increase which have been marked in entry register maintain by library.

Problems Encountered and Recourses Required –

Users are always playing with their mobile phones (smart phones) which offer opportunity to central library, but if they do not have QR code scanner they might have failed to read those journals and magazines. There is only few resources require to implement this service, exact links of available journals and magazines and QR code scanner which is available freely download from google Playstore.

Output of practice –

It has positive impact on users reading ability, they are always curious about existing automated library services.

2. Title of the practice – Online Attendance System through Smart Card

Goals –

- To smooth functioning of existing attendance system with smart card
- To provide access of Attendance Report to learners and parents
- To ensure maximum presenty of learners

The Context –

School Information Management Software - According to digitaledu.net “School Information Management Software (SIMS) offers all powerful functions to keep daily management chores to the least possible levels”.

Following table shows the main features of online attendance system which is implemented by college to monitor day-to-day attendance of learners.

Table – 1	Table - 2																											
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Online Attendance App

The online attendance app offers to learners exhaustive reports of their presenty in class rooms, beside that there is availability of separate apps to their parents with username and password.

The apps is free available to download to all learners from google playstore. The app is namely, “InSync” is fully integrated with Student Information Management System offered by DigitalEdu IT Solutions Pvt Ltd. InSync is all-in-one solution for administration, management and governance of any educational organization”. Using this app parents can stay up-to-date with their kid's school information such as Notices,

Alerts, Messages, Attendance, Classroom Lessons, Home-works, Fees, School Bus Status. Parent can also communicate with other parents.

Evidence of Success –

Sr. No.	Class	Students Connected to Online Attendance System
1	Accounting & Finance	All Learners 350+
2	Biotechnology	All Learners 200+
3	Information Technology	All Learners 300+
4	Computer Science	All Learners 250+
5	Management Studies	All Learners 350+

All learners are added by Online Attendance system by default, while admission procedure is conducted simultaneously learners are allocated SIMS id to recognize through their smart card by the system to mark his/her attendance online.

Presently total 1595 learners are get benefited by this online attendance system, according to survey conducted by central library all are frequently visit to Report of their own through InSync mobile apps.

Problems Encountered and Recourses Required –

Duplication of Scheduling work – There is semester based pattern implemented while develop the system according to University norms. Teachers have to be done scheduling of their classes twice in year and it is make duplications type work.

There is need of RFID device which recognize the smart card details and same recorded in it which can be fetch while importing data from device to system. Users are always play with their mobile phones (smart phones) which offer opportunity to central library, but if they do not have QR code scanner they might have failed to read those journals and magazines. There is only few resources require to implement this service, exact links of available journals and magazines and QR code scanner which is available freely download from google Playstore.

Output of practice –

Once the system has been implemented, learners get their active reports on their mobile phones and parents are also quite feel secured. Manual attendance use to take minimum 5-10min time whereas Smart Card completes this task within 3-5min. Therefore, learners get more time to learn during the session. One single click cloud based important reports are available to all Teachers, Learners and Parents which have positive impact on learners learning process.

3. Title of the practice – Employability Training Programme

Goals –

- To sensitize about the opportunities available in corporate sector
- To develop soft skills amongst the learners

The Context –

The Employability Training Programme is organizing in collaboration with Tata Consultancy Services, Pune. The programme intends to reach out to the unemployed graduates, B.A., B.Sc., B.Com., B.B.A. to make them employable by imparting training free of cost and then consider them for employment in the TCS company, subject to their complying with the company's standard norms. The Programme focus is on the SC/ST unemployed graduates. The programme consist to develop a person's communication skill, numerical and analytical ability, it enables one to face interviews confidently. Grooming and etiquette sessions

familiarize a candidate with corporate environment. The college learners who are regular in attendance will be eligible for a participation certificate from TCS which will increase their employability in the corporate world. Post training there will be an exit test. Those who qualify will be taken through interview rounds. Successful candidates will be absorbed finally in TCS

Training and duration: The training hours per day varies between 4 to 7 hours, depending on the convenience of the trainees as well as the trainer. In certain places, residential training has been conducted where in addition to the English training and computer training; candidates are exposed to certain sports activities for overall personality development and sportsman spirit. So the entire training spans throughout the day. Total training generally includes 80 hours of English, 10 hours of computers and 10 hours of analytical thinking. However, the duration for each module can be tweaked depending upon the profile of the batch.

Evidence of Success –

Certificates of Training Completion by learners issued and separate file has been maintained in central library. Learners are also get an opportunity to work with TCS after successfully completion of their training session.

Problem Encountered –

The programme is organized during the instruction days of learners; therefore it is become difficult to attend the programme for learners, though few of them have completed the same successfully.

Output of Practice –

Report of Employability Training Programme 2014 - 2015

In collaboration with Tata Consultancy Services

Sr. No.	Class	Total no. of students enrolled for Training Programme	Total no. of students completed Employability Training Programme	Total no. of students got Job Opportunity with TCS
1	T.Y.B.A.	20	05	Nil
2	T.Y.B.COM.	26	12	Nil
3	T.Y.B.M.S.	04	03	01
4	T.Y. A & F	10	09	06
5	T.Y.B.SC.	18	07	01
Total		78	36	08

4. Title of the practice – Guidelines seminar on Airline Industry

Goals –

- To sensitize about the opportunities available in Airline Industry
- To develop soft skills amongst the learners
- To create awareness of Government scholarship available for learners

The Context –

The Guidance seminar on Airlines Industry is organizing in collaboration with National Commission for Schedule Caste, Government of India, New Delhi for learners belonging to SC, ST, and OBC category. The seminar was focus on opportunities available in Airlines Industry and career guidance with help of Government scholarship for students.

Pilot Mr. A. D. Manek (Founder Skyline Industry) was invited as a Resource Person for this guidance seminar, and Mr. Milind Lavate, District Coordinator-NCSC, Maharashtra provide details information about the programme.

Evidence of Success –

There were more than hundreds of participant from our college was participated and learners from other colleges also allowed to participate in this seminar. Registration forms are issued to all participant of this seminar.

Problems Encountered –

The seminar was successfully organized at Changu Kana Thakur Arts, Commerce and Science College; New Panvel on 20th February 2015 at Resource Centre, but the training available in future will be charge by the organization except the participate those who have passed their entrance exam. The seminar is focus only SC, ST, and OBC learners others are not eligible to get grants from Government to do their career in Airline Industry. Therefore, responses from General category students were very low as far as participation is concern.

Output of Practice –

There was huge demand from learners to organize such type of seminar in our colleges. Few of our college learners were selected for their entrance examination and interviews.

Evolving the library as a learning resource centre is the continuous process whereas library collection, services, facilities are keep on changing according to users need. With help of innovative practices or best practices one can achieve optimum utilization of learning resources.

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